

PERFORMANCE OF PMFBY (PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA) IN LATUR DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA STATE

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MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised: 08.10.2024; MS Accepted: 09.10.2024

MS 3296

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,)

Abstract

The study evaluates the performance of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Maharashtra, specifically focusing on Latur district, and offers recommendations for its effective implementation. By analysing a sample of 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers, the research investigates the scheme's impact on farmers' income stability from the period 2016-17 to 2022-23. The results indicated a significant positive growth rate at the national, state, and district levels, underscoring the crucial role of insurance compensation in risk management. The findings revealed that compensation mechanisms contribute to more consistent agricultural production and improved financial stability for farmers, emphasizing the importance of effective agricultural insurance schemes. Furthermore, the study identifies various constraints faced by sampled insured farmers, including delays in compensation, insufficient compensation amounts, and dissatisfaction with coverage options. These challenges point to essential areas for improvement within the PMFBY framework. The suggestions provided by respondents served as valuable insights for policymakers aiming to enhance the effectiveness and accessibility of crop insurance. Overall, this paper highlights the positive effects of the PMFBY on income stability and emphasizes the need for ongoing improvements to support farmers more effectively in Latur district.

Keywords: PMFBY, Growth rate, Insured farmers, Income stability, Constraints, Suggestions.

Introduction

India's agriculture sector is vital to its economy, contributing 18.2 % to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and supporting approximately 42.3 % of the population. www.fao.org However, the sector faces significant risks, including production variability due to climate change, pests, and diseases, leading to adverse economic outcomes like farmer migration, unemployment, and poverty. Effective risk management is essential, with crop insurance serving as a crucial tool to mitigate financial losses from natural disasters. Crop insurance in India began in 1972, evolving through various schemes such as the Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS) and the National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS). Despite these efforts, issues like delayed claims and high premiums hindered effectiveness. This prompted the introduction of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in 2016, aiming to enhance coverage and affordability for farmers. PMFBY is designed to provide comprehensive insurance against crop failures, with premium rates set at 2% for *kharif* crops, 1.5% for *rabi* crops, and 5% for commercial crops (www.pmfby.gov.in) The scheme emphasizes quick claim settlements and uses modern technology for assessing crop yields, thus encouraging farmers to adopt innovative practices. Implemented through various stakeholders, including the Ministry of Agriculture and state governments, PMFBY aims to support farmers' income stability and promote sustainable agricultural practices. Researching PMFBY reveals its potential impact on farmers' livelihoods, access to credit, and overall agricultural resilience. By ensuring financial support in the face of crop losses, PMFBY contributes to rural development and food security. The scheme's focus on inclusivity enables small and marginal farmers to benefit, thereby enhancing the agricultural economy's stability and growth. This paper examines the implementation and impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Latur district of Maharashtra, a region particularly vulnerable to drought.

The study aims to assess farmers' awareness, the scheme's effectiveness in providing financial support during crop failures, and its influence on income stability and agricultural practices. PMFBY represents a significant advancement in India's approach to agricultural insurance, addressing past shortcomings and providing a necessary safety net for farmers amidst increasing agricultural risks. PMFBY offers comprehensive insurance coverage for food crops, oilseeds, and annual commercial/horticultural crops based on historical yield data. It is compulsory for farmers with crop loans but voluntary for others. The scheme implements an area-based approach for loss assessment and utilizes modern technologies like remote sensing for accurate yield

estimation. This research paper aims to analyse the key constraints faced by PMFBY-insured farmers, identify the factors limiting their access to the scheme's benefits, and gather suggestions from the farmers themselves to improve its implementation. By focusing on the perspectives of the insured farmers, this study seeks to contribute to policy discussions that could help reform the PMFBY and make it more farmer-centric and responsive to their needs.

Objectives

1. To study the progress of PMFBY in Latur district of Maharashtra state
2. To analyze the impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers
3. To identify the weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest suitable measures for its improvement

Materials And Methods

The research employed a comprehensive methodology combining both quantitative and qualitative techniques to assess the impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Latur district of Maharashtra, India. The study was purposively conducted in Latur district of the Marathwada region of Maharashtra state in the year 2023-24, focusing on four tahsils—Latur, Ausa, Nilanga, and Udgir were selected for having the maximum number of insured farmers under PMFBY. From each tahsil, three villages were chosen, and within each village, 10 insured and 10 non-insured farmers were randomly selected, resulting in a total sample size of 240 farmers. Primary data were collected in year 2023-24 through structured questionnaires, targeting socio-economic indicators, farming practices, and income stability.

Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were utilized to interpret the data, including the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) to assess PMFBY's progress. CAGR was calculated using secondary data collected from www.pmfby.gov.in for the years 2016-17 to 2022-23 (covering both *kharif* and *rabi* seasons). T-test was used for calculating t-value. Various income stability measures, such as mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation, were employed to analyse the data further. Additionally, Garrett's Ranking Technique was applied to identify weaknesses in PMFBY implementation and suggest improvements. Secondary data complemented the analysis, providing contextual insights into historical trends and performance metrics of agricultural insurance in India. Constraints were gathered through open-ended questions, and suggestions were also collected from the insured farmers.

Results and Discussion

The study analysed the performance of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) scheme, with the help of compound annual growth rate (CAGR), income satability and various constraints impacting the significance based on mean scores and ranks. The detailed results are outlined below. The year wise data on number of insured farmers, area insured, reported claims, approved claims, total claims paid and total farmer's benefited during *kharif* and *rabi* under PMFBY in Latur district for the last 8 years *i.e.*, 2016 to 2023 have been collected from the www.pmfby.gov.in.

Table 1. Provides insights into the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of insured farmers. It compares the growth rates of insured farmers for *kharif* and *rabi* seasons from the period 2016 to 2023 at three levels: India, Maharashtra, and Latur. At national overview the CAGR for insured farmers in the *kharif* season was -7 percent per annum, indicating a significant decline in the number of insured farmers at the national level. This negative growth suggests challenges in increasing insurance coverage for *kharif* crops. The CAGR for the *rabi* season was -2 percent per annum, which was also negative but less severe compared to *kharif*. This smaller decline might reflect slightly better performance or fewer challenges in the insurance uptake for *rabi* crops. Maharashtra showed a positive CAGR of 20 percent per annum for the *kharif* season, which was a significant improvement compared to the national trend. The CAGR for the *rabi* season in Maharashtra was 3 percent per annum, reflecting a positive but more modest growth compared to *kharif*. Latur exhibits a CAGR of 1 percent per annum for the *kharif* season, indicating minimal growth. The CAGR for *rabi* in Latur was 3 percent per annum, showing a positive growth similar to the state-level data but still modest.

Table 2. Presents the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of the cropped area insured under PMFBY. It compares the growth rates of insured area for *kharif* and *rabi* seasons at three levels: National, State, and District (Latur) level from year *kharif* 2016 to *kharif* 2023. The CAGR for the insured area during the *kharif* season was 1 percent per annum, indicating a modest increase at the India level. This positive growth suggests a gradual improvement in the area covered by insurance for *kharif* crops. The CAGR for the *rabi* season was also 1 percent per annum, showing similar modest growth as in *kharif*. This consistency indicates that the improvements in insurance coverage are uniform across seasons. Maharashtra showed a notably high CAGR of 19 percent per annum for the *kharif* season, indicating substantial growth in the insured area. This impressive growth reflects successful state-level initiatives or policies that have significantly increased insurance coverage for *kharif* crops. The CAGR for *rabi* in Maharashtra was 4 percent per annum, indicating positive growth but at a lower rate compared to *kharif*. Latur showed a CAGR of 1 percent per annum for the *kharif* season, similar to the national growth rate. This indicated that the growth in the insured area was in line with national trends but suggests limited progress compared to the state-level performance. The similar growth rate to the national level might reflect specific local challenges or barriers that limit the growth in Latur. The CAGR for *rabi* in Latur was 4 percent per annum, aligning with the state-level growth rate for this season. This indicated that while Latur's growth was consistent with Maharashtra's overall performance for *rabi*, it still lags behind the significant growth observed for *kharif* in Maharashtra. Similar results were found by Patwardhan and Narwade (2014), who revealed that the period 2003 to 2004 a growth is observed in number of farmers in Latur district as compared to 2000.

The Table 3 provides data on the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims for crop insurance across India, Maharashtra and Latur district. The CAGR for reported claims in the *kharif* season was 8 percent per annum, indicating a positive growth rate at the national level. The CAGR for the *Rabi* season was 44 percent per annum, which shows a very high positive growth rate. This substantial increase suggests a significant rise in reported claims for *rabi* crops. Maharashtra showed a CAGR of -41 percent per annum for *kharif*, indicating a substantial decline in reported claims. This negative

growth suggests that the number or value of claims reported for *kharif* crops in Maharashtra has significantly decreased. The CAGR for *rabi* claims in Maharashtra was 1 percent per annum, showing a modest positive growth. Latur has a CAGR of 2 percent per annum for reported claims during the *kharif* season, reflecting a positive but relatively modest growth. The CAGR for *rabi* claims in Latur was 5 percent per annum, showing moderate positive growth. This increase is lower than the national average for *rabi* but indicates a rising trend in reported claims.

Table 4. provides data on the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approved claims for crop insurance. The CAGR for approved claims in the *kharif* season was -60 percent per annum, indicating a significant decline in the rate at which claims are approved nationally. This substantial decrease suggests systemic issues in the claims approval process, which could include stricter claim validation procedures, delays in processing, or a reduction in the overall number of claims that meet approval criteria. The CAGR for approved claims in the *rabi* season was -26 percent per annum, which also showed a negative growth but less severe than *kharif*. Maharashtra showed a CAGR of -42 percent per annum for approved claims in the *kharif* season, representing a substantial decline. The CAGR for *rabi* in Maharashtra was 3, showing a positive growth rate. This increase suggests an improvement in the approval process for *rabi* claims. Latur exhibits a CAGR of 8 percent per annum for approved claims during the *kharif* season, indicating a positive growth rate. This suggests that Latur has seen an improvement in the approval of *kharif* claims. The CAGR for *rabi* claims in Latur was 7 percent per annum, showing a positive growth similar to the *kharif* season. This positive growth suggests that Latur is performing relatively well in terms of approving claims for both seasons.

Table 5. compares the growth rates of total claims paid for *kharif* and *rabi* seasons at three levels: India, Maharashtra, and Latur. The CAGR for total claims paid in the *kharif* season was -5 percent per annum, indicating a slight decline in the amount of claims paid at the national level. The CAGR for total claims paid in the *rabi* season was -20 percent per annum, showing a more significant decline compared to *kharif*. This substantial decrease suggests that financial support for *rabi* crop losses has reduced significantly. Maharashtra showed a CAGR of 7 percent per annum for total claims paid in the *kharif* season, reflecting positive growth. The CAGR for total claims paid in Maharashtra for the *rabi* season was -13 percent per annum, indicating a decline similar to the national trend but less severe. Latur exhibited a CAGR of -7 percent per annum for total claims paid during the *kharif* season, indicating a decline similar to the national trend but less severe. This suggests that the amount of claims paid in Latur for *kharif* crops has decreased, which could be attributed to lower claim amounts or fewer claims being processed and paid. The CAGR for total claims paid in Latur for *rabi* was -17 percent per annum, reflecting a significant decline. The results are also similar with Patwardhan and Narwade (2014), who revealed that in the period 2001 claim amount paid 2196.46 lakhs showed a growth in Latur district as compared to 2000.

Table 6. represents the CAGR values reflect the annualized growth rate of the number of farmers who have received benefits from insurance, highlighting trends and regional performance in terms of reaching and supporting farmers. The CAGR for total farmers benefiting from insurance in the *kharif* season was -6 percent per annum, indicating a decline at the national level. This suggests a reduction in the number of farmers receiving insurance benefits for *kharif* crops. The CAGR for total farmers benefiting from insurance in the *rabi* season was -19 percent per annum, reflecting a more significant decline compared to *kharif*. This substantial decrease suggests that fewer farmers are benefiting from insurance for *rabi* crops. Maharashtra showed a CAGR of 1 percent per annum for the total number of farmers benefiting from insurance in the *kharif* season, indicating a slight increase. This suggests that Maharashtra has seen a modest improvement in the number of farmers receiving benefits for *kharif* crops. The CAGR for

rabi benefits in Maharashtra was -19 percent per annum, showing a significant decline similar to the national trend. This decline indicates that despite some improvements for *kharif*, the number of farmers benefiting from insurance for *rabi* crops has reduced significantly. Latur exhibited a CAGR of -8 percent per annum for the total number of farmers benefiting from insurance during the *kharif* season, reflecting a decline. The CAGR for *rabi* benefits in Latur was -12 percent per annum, indicating a significant decline but less severe than the national average for *rabi*. This reduction suggests that while there is a drop in the number of farmers benefiting from insurance, it is not as pronounced as the national decline. The reasons might include localized issues or varying effectiveness of insurance schemes. This is in agreement with results of Patwardhan and Narwade (2014), who concluded that in all the districts of Marathwada region farmers covered, area covered and claim paid under NAIS have decreased under study period (2000-2010).

The results of the analysis of Table 7 illustrate a clear advantage of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in enhancing gross yield for farmers in Latur district. The mean gross yield without compensation is ₹103,791.79, while with compensation, it rises significantly to ₹131,634.19. This represents an increase of approximately 26.8%, indicating that access to crop insurance substantially boosts farmers' financial outcomes. Moreover, the standard deviation of gross yield without compensation is ₹43,524.50, compared to ₹39,587.18 with compensation. This reduction in standard deviation indicates that yields are more consistent among insured farmers, as reflected in the coefficient of variation, which decreases from 0.41 to 0.30. This change suggests that the income variability is lower for farmers with insurance, highlighting enhanced income stability. The income index further supports these findings, with values of 0.59 for non-insured farmers and 0.70 for those with compensation. This increase in the income index signifies that insured farmers experience a more stable income, as values closer to 1 indicate greater stability. Overall, these results underscore the critical role of PMFBY in improving financial security and reducing income variability among farmers, thereby fostering greater agricultural resilience in the region. Table.8 shows the constraints faced by the insured farmers in adoption of PMFBY. The most pressing issue is delays in compensation realization (mean score: 71.45), which significantly affects farmers' financial stability post-loss. Farmers often find compensation inadequate to cover actual losses, ranking this issue second (mean score: 66.04). A significant percentage of farmers are unhappy with the crops covered by the insurance scheme (44%). The criteria for insurance claims are seen as inefficient (46%), complicating the claims process for farmers. Lack of transparency in claim settlements (39%) is noted as a substantial concern, highlighting the need for clearer processes. Poor service or lack of cooperation from banks (37%), which are often involved in facilitating insurance transactions, is a notable constraint. This suggests that the relationship between banks and farmers needs to be improved to provide better support and service in the insurance process. Farmers are also dissatisfied with the indemnity levels (36%) provided by the insurance schemes. This dissatisfaction indicates that the payout levels may not be sufficient to cover the extent of their losses. Lack of faith in the scheme (32%) or agency reflects a broader issue of trust and confidence in the insurance system. Building credibility and trust through improved communication, better service, and consistent outcomes is essential to address this concern. The absence of a local grievance redressed mechanism (31%) means that farmers have limited options to resolve issues or disputes with their insurance claims. Establishing local mechanisms for addressing grievances can help ensure that farmers. Poor coordination between farmers and implementing agencies (29%) hinders the effective implementation of insurance schemes. Improved coordination can lead to better communication, understanding, and overall efficiency in the administration of insurance policies. The issue of having a threshold yield lower than the actual yield (26%) suggests a mismatch between the insurance coverage and actual farming

conditions. Adjusting threshold yields to more accurately reflect actual farming conditions could improve the relevance and effectiveness of the insurance coverage. Lack of awareness about available facilities (25%) points to a need for better information dissemination and farmer education. Ignorance about the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) (23%) indicates that there is a gap in understanding specific insurance schemes among farmers. Increased outreach and education about PMFBY can help improve participation and satisfaction. Challenges with paperwork processing and compensation (22%) highlight administrative inefficiencies. Streamlining the paperwork process and simplifying compensation procedures can reduce bureaucratic delays and make the insurance scheme more user-friendly.

Table.9 describes the suggestions given by the farmers for improvement of PMFBY. The insured farmers in the research region were also asked for their suggestion thoughts on how to overcome the constraints. One of the most pressing needs ranked first identified by farmers is the ability to track their insurance status and claims online (68.33%). This digital transparency is vital, as it fosters trust and ensures that farmers are informed about their insurance processes. Additionally, the demand for a transparent settlement process (64.17%) emphasizes the importance of clarity in how claims are handled. Farmers expressed a strong desire for quick settlements (61.67%), recognizing that timely compensation is essential for their financial stability after a loss. Promoting digital literacy among farmers is another significant concern (55.83%). Many farmers lack the skills needed to navigate online systems effectively, which can hinder their ability to enroll in PMFBY. Enhancing digital skills through targeted training programs could empower farmers and facilitate greater participation in the scheme. Furthermore, implementing a Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) system would streamline the disbursement of funds, ensuring that payouts are received promptly, thereby alleviating financial stress during crises. Accessibility is also crucial, with farmers advocating for insurance services to be available at their doorsteps or within their villages. This localized approach would ensure that even those in remote areas can access necessary services without facing barriers. Additionally, the development of a dedicated PMFBY mobile app could provide a centralized platform for farmers to obtain information and manage their insurance, further enhancing user engagement. Farmers also expressed the need for broader crop coverage under PMFBY. By including more crops, the program could cater to a diverse range of agricultural practices, encouraging wider participation. Simplifying the online application process through a user-friendly website would also facilitate easier access for farmers seeking insurance. The establishment of a public-grievance settlement mechanism at the local level was highlighted as a way to address issues promptly, fostering a more responsive and supportive environment for farmers. Moreover, assessing individual farms rather than relying solely on village-level assessments could lead to more accurate compensation based on actual losses experienced. Utilizing local governance structures, such as Grampanchayats, for loss assessment could enhance community involvement and ensure culturally appropriate practices. Engaging farmers through social media for feedback collection presents an innovative way to gather insights and foster a sense of community. Additionally, improving access to PMFBY for small and marginal farmers is essential for ensuring that all agricultural stakeholders can benefit from the program.

Conclusion

The analysis of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Latur district reveals both the potential benefits and significant challenges associated with the scheme. While access to crop insurance has shown to enhance gross yields and improve income stability for insured farmers, the overall uptake and satisfaction with the program remain concerning. The decline in the number of insured farmers, alongside negative trends in claims and benefits, underscores systemic issues in the claims process, inadequate compensation levels, and limited transparency. Farmers' feedback highlights the urgent need for

improved digital engagement, transparent processes, and greater accessibility to insurance services.

The policy implications of these findings are critical for enhancing the effectiveness of PMFBY. First, there is a clear necessity for streamlining the claims process to ensure timely and adequate compensation, which could rebuild trust and encourage greater participation among farmers. Additionally, fostering digital literacy and creating user-friendly platforms can help farmers navigate the insurance system more effectively. Policymakers should consider expanding the range of crops covered under PMFBY and implementing direct benefit transfer systems to facilitate quicker access to funds. Finally, establishing local grievance redress mechanisms and involving community governance structures in the loss assessment process can enhance transparency and accountability, ultimately leading to a more resilient agricultural sector. Addressing these issues holistically will be essential to realize the full potential of PMFBY and support the livelihoods of farmers in the region.

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Table 1. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.		Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7**	-2**
		t value	-1.98	-0.62
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20	3**
		t value	2.98	0.25
3	Latur	CAGR	1**	3**
		t value	0.13	0.30

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 2. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of area insured under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.		Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	1**	1**
		t value	0.51	0.34
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19**	4**
		t value	1.34	0.29
3	Latur	CAGR	1**	4**
		t value	0.42	0.39

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 3. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.		Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	8**	44**
		t value	2.41	1.75
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41**	1**
		t value	-1.52	0.04
3	Latur	CAGR	2**	5**
		t value	0.39	0.71

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 4. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approved claims under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sl. No.		Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-60**	-26**
		t value	-2.47	-0.84
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42**	3**
		t value	-1.57	0.11
3	Latur	CAGR	8**	7**
		t value	1.74	1.03

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 5. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of total claims paid under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23 (Kharif & Rabi).

Sl. No.		Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-5**	-20**
		t value	-1.01	-2.35
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7**	-13**
		t value	0.83	-0.55
3	Latur	CAGR	-7**	-17**
		t value	-0.82	-0.67

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 6. Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of total farmers benefited under PMFBY for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23 (Kharif & Rabi).

Sl. No.		Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-6**	-19**
		t value	-3.02	-2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	1**	-19**
		t value	0.11	-0.73
3	Latur	CAGR	-8**	-12**
		t value	-1.08	-0.72

Note: **Significant at 5% level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 7. Income stability and income index of sample insured farmers for the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Particulars	Gross yield without compensation	Gross yield with compensation
Mean	103791.79	131634.19
Standard Deviation	43524.5	39587.18
Coefficient of Covariation	0.41	0.30

Income Index	0.59	0.70
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Table 8: Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers by Garrett's ranking

Sl.No.	Constraints	Garrett's mean score	Percentage	Garrett's Rank
1	Insufficient compensation	66.04	46	II
2	Delay in realization of compensation	71.45	50	I
3	Not satisfied with crops covered	62.82	44	III
4	Criteria about crop insurance claim is inefficient	59.92	42	IV
5	No transparency in claim settlement	56.79	39	V
6	Lack of service / co-operation from the bank	53.04	37	VI
7	Not satisfied with indemnity level	51.83	36	VII
8	No faith in scheme / agency opinion	46.04	32	VIII
9	No mechanism to redress grievances at local level	44.54	31	IX
10	No proper coordination of farmers and implementing agencies	42.25	29	X
11	Threshold yield is lower than the actual yield	37.93	26	XI
12	Difficulties in processing and compensation of paper work.	32.01	22	XIV
13	Ignorance about PMFBY	32.57	23	XIII
14	Not aware of the facilities available	35.74	25	XII

Fig. 1 Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers**Table 9. Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY**

Sl.no	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Enable farmers to track their insurance status & claims online	82	68.33	I
2	Need for transparency in settlement of claims	77	64.17	II
3	Quick settlement of claims	74	61.67	III
4	Promote digital literacy among farmers for PMFBY enrollment.	67	55.83	IV
5	Implement direct benefit transfer (DBT)	62	51.67	V
6	Insurance service at doorstep / at village level	60	50.00	VI
7	Develop a dedicated PMFBY mobile app for farmers.	57	47.50	VII

8	Cover more crops	53	44.17	VIII
9	Make the website user friendly for online application	48	40.00	IX
10	Public-grievance settlement mechanism at local level	44	36.67	X
11	Individual farm as unit of assessment instead of village	41	34.17	XI
12	Grampanchayat as a unit of loss assessment	40	33.33	XII
13	Utilize social media platforms for feedback collection.	38	31.67	XIII
14	Improve accessibility of PMFBY to small and marginal farmers.	34	28.33	XIV
15	Create awareness about the benefits available	26	21.67	XV

Fig. 2 Suggestions given by sample insured farmers for improvement in PMFBY